

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

Preparation of 5 α ,6 α -epoxy (2a, 3a) and 5 β ,6 β -epoxides (2b, 3b) of 3 β -alkyl ether (1a, 1b). A typical experiment: (25 R)-5-Spirosten-3 β -alkyl ether (4 g) was mixed with perbenzoic acid (25 ml, 2 mol) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.1 g) as a catalyst and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether-chloroform mixture. The organic extract was washed successively with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate, 5% hydrochloric acid and finally with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded an oily substance which was recrystallised from acetone (3 g, 75%). Its tlc showed two spots in benzene-ethyl acetate (3:1) mixture with relative proportion of α - and β -isomers (80:20). The repeated fractional crystallisation of the mixture (2 g) using ethyl acetate gave the α -epoxide (2a or 3a; 1.6 g, 80%) and the mother liquor on repeated crystallisation gave the β -epoxide (2b or 3b; 0.4 g, 20%).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
2a	205-07	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$	75.67 (75.8)	9.90 (9.95)	—
2b	210-12	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$	75.67 (75.8)	9.90 (9.95)	—
3a	197-99	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_4$	75.98 (76.0)	10.04 (10.0)	—
3b	203-05	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_4$	75.98 (76.0)	10.04 (10.0)	—
4a	192-94	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$	73.04 (73.1)	9.56 (9.6)	—
4b	188-90	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_4$	73.41 (73.8)	9.70 (9.80)	—
5a	118-20	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	70.73 (71.2)	9.47 (9.5)	2.94 (3.0)
5b	163-65	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	71.16 (71.4)	9.61 (9.9)	2.86 (2.9)
6a	170-72	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4\text{N}$	73.52 (73.8)	9.40 (9.6)	3.06 (3.1)
6b	183-85	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_4\text{N}$	73.88 (74.2)	9.55 (9.8)	2.97 (3.1)

The preparation of (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -alkyl ether (4a, 4b), its corresponding oximes (5a, 5b) and seco-nitriles (6a, 6b) were carried out according to the procedure reported earlier².

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activities of New Quinoline 8-Thioglycollyhydrazones

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QUINOLINE ring derivatives are well-known for their varied spectrum of pharmacological activities. The compounds are claimed to possess antispasmodics¹. The most effective and the best known pharmacology of chincona has been reviewed². Mishra and Saxena³ reported that some quinolines are active against *E. histolytica*. On the other hand, the physiologically active substituted-hydrazones are of immense importance and various hydrazones derivatives are associated with anthelmintic, antifungal and antibacterial activities⁴. A large number of hydrazones have also been used as selective sensitive reagents for determination of copper and other metals⁵. With these in view it was anticipated that quinoline derivatives substituted at 8-position would prove of pharmacological interest. In continuation of our studies on hydrazones as potential drugs, we have synthesised several new quinoline 8-thioglycollyhydrazones (Scheme 1) in which the primary amino group of hydrazide undergoes condensation with ketonic groups resulting the formation of hydrazones.

Starting from quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrazide we have prepared unreported hydrazones

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL, AND SELECTED IR SPECTRAL, (cm⁻¹)* DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν _{NH}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}	
						O	H	N				
1.	CH ₃	CH ₂ COCH ₃	201-2	60	Cream	60.62 (60.95)	4.79 (5.39)	12.97 (13.33)	—	3 220br	1 680m 1 650s	1 590w
2.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	138-39	40	Pale yellow	68.11 (68.05)	4.64 (5.07)	12.71 (12.53)	3 400s	3 180m	1 660s	1 590m
3.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₂ COCH ₃	163	60	Cream	66.42 (66.84)	4.73 (5.03)	10.83 (11.14)	3 490m	—	1 640s	1 620sh
4.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	156	50	Cream	68.84 (68.76)	5.97 (5.44)	11.81 (12.03)	3 300br	3 140m	1 640m	1 620sh
5.	H	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	200	80	Light yellow	68.63 (69.16)	4.35 (4.89)	11.81 (12.10)	—	3 170m	1 660s	1 590m
6.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	161	50	Cream	72.72 (72.54)	4.27 (4.78)	10.91 (10.57)	3 260m	—	1 655s	1 580w
7.	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	155-56	50	Cream	58.83 (59.01)	3.37 (3.82)	15.14 (15.30)	—	3 160s	1 648s	1 620sh
8.	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	198-99	65	Cream	59.65 (59.01)	3.62 (3.82)	15.64 (15.30)	—	3 180w	1 680s	1 610w
9.	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	221-22	70	Yellow	58.78 (59.01)	4.51 (3.82)	15.00 (15.30)	—	3 170m	1 670m	1 620m
10.	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	148	40	Pale yellow	60.12 (60.75)	4.23 (3.93)	11.83 (11.81)	3 400br	—	1 670s	1 590w
11.	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	188	70	Cream	63.81 (64.09)	4.11 (4.45)	12.16 (12.46)	—	3 140w	1 650s	1 620sh
12.	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	220	50	Yellow	64.77 (64.09)	3.98 (4.45)	12.92 (12.46)	—	3 280w	1 660s	1 595w
13.	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	188	60	Yellowish white	64.61 (64.95)	4.11 (4.48)	12.54 (11.96)	3 410s	3 120w	1 640s	1 595m
14.	C ₆ H ₅	CO-C ₆ H ₅	191-92	80	Pale yellow	70.13 (70.58)	4.11 (4.47)	9.43 (9.88)	—	3 140w	1 650s	1 620sh
15.	R ₁ =R ₂ =Isatin		212	70	Deep yellow	63.31 (63.98)	3.97 (3.86)	15.11 (15.46)	—	3 220w	1 725m 1 680s	1 590w
16.	R ₁ =R ₂ =Acenaphthene quinone		195	60	Brown	69.21 (69.52)	3.33 (3.77)	10.19 (10.57)	3 430m	3 180w	1 675m	1 625m

*s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, br=broad, sh=shoulder.

with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes, *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, acetylacetone, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, acetophenone, benzophenone, acetylacetone, propiophenone, benzil, isatine and acenaphthenequinone.

Experimental

The compounds were characterised by elemental analyse and ir spectral data. Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

Quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrazide : Quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrochloride⁶ (10.0 g) was refluxed with absolute alcohol (50 ml) for 10 h in a dry condition. Hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) was then added and refluxed further for 3 h. The excess of solvent was distilled off and the resulting precipitate was washed with alcohol, purified with animal charcoal and crystallised from methanol, (60%), m.p. 170-71°.

Quinoline 8-thioglycollyl hydrazones : To the alcoholic solution of quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrazide, an alcoholic solution of the appropriate aldehyde or ketone was added and refluxed for 5 h. The resulting solid mass after cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

The quinoline 8-thioglycollyl hydrazones are crystalline in nature and the colour varied from yellow to orange. All are stable under dry condition and soluble in polar solvents. They showed no change in their physical properties even after a long time. The ir spectra of the hydrazones exhibited characteristic bands at 3 400-3 100 (NH), 1 700-1 640 (C=O) and 1 625-1 590 cm⁻¹ (C=N) (Table 1).

The pathological investigation of all the compounds were screened for antimicrobial activities using agar plate disk⁷ diffusion technique on *Streptophylococcus aureus*, *S. albus*, *Proteus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pyocyanea* bacteria. An impregnating small disk of a standard filter paper with given amount of a hydrazone was placed on a plate of culture medium inoculated with the organism. Among the compounds, the compound with sl. no. 13, i.e. hydrazone derived from quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrazide and 2-hydroxyacetophenone, is moderately active against all the five bacteria. But all the other compounds were found inactive.

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Chemical Constituents of *Ulva fasciata* from Indian Coast†

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ULVA fasciata, a green alga (Chlorophyta) belonging to family *Ulvaceae* is of wide occurrence along the Malvan region of the western coast (Arabian Sea) of the Indian peninsula. Some species of the genus *Ulva* are reported to be used as human and animal foods, as well as for medicine and manure^{1,2}, *U. rigida* Ag., a species from the Black Sea region has been extensively studied for its sterol constituents³. The present studies also revealed the presence of β -sitosterol, isofucosterol and saringosterol, the common sterols of *Ulvaceae*, the latter being the major sterol of *U. fasciata*.

An alcoholic extract of *U. fasciata*, when subjected to a broad biological screening, under a

programme of screening of marine organisms of the Indian Ocean and coastal region⁴ in this Institute, showed antiviral activity *in vivo* against Semliki Forest Virus (SFV) at 2.0 mg/mouse giving 50% protection. In the present communication, the compounds isolated from *U. fasciata* are reported for the first time.

Experimental

¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on 90 MHz with TMS as internal standard, and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker WM 400 MHz super-conduction FT spectrometer. Gc of fatty hydrocarbon was carried on Chemito-3800 using Dexil column, while gc of methyl esters of FFA was carried on a Pye-Unicam 104 instrument using 10% DEGS column, standard used being methyl oleate.

Seaweed material: *U. fasciata* was collected in June 1985 by National Institute of Oceanography, Goa, India⁴ from Malvan region of western Coast of India and a Voucher Specimen of the alga is preserved in the herbarium of NIO, Goa, India.

Extraction and isolation: The shed-dried sea weed (4.0 kg) was powdered and extracted with ethanol (90-95%) at room temperature. The alcoholic extract was concentrated (~1.0 dm³) and fractionated to give hexane (3.0 g), chloroform (27.0 g), n-butanol (1.0 g) and water-soluble fraction consisted mostly of inorganic salts.

The combined hexane-chloroform fraction was divided into two parts. Part-A was saponified for its fatty acid contents and part-B was carefully chromatographed over an alumina column using solvents of increasing polarity. Elution with hexane gave a mixture of the fatty hydrocarbons (F 005-F 007). The CI-ms of the mixture showed the presence of closely related C₃₀ to C₃₆ fatty hydrocarbons. Continued elution with hexane-benzene (95:5) yielded fraction F008 as a viscous mass, tlc single spot, gc (R_f=9.6') analysed for methyl ester of heptadecanoic acid by nmr and ms. Elution with hexane-benzene (90:10) gave fraction F009 which exhibited a high order of antiviral activity at 0.3 mg/mouse/7 days giving 80% protection against SF virus and was found to be a complex mixture of fatty matter which is under investigation. Further elution of the column with hexane-benzene (80:20) yielded palmitic acid (70.0 mg), m.p. 64°, C₁₆H₃₂O₂ (M⁺ 256 m/z) (ir, ms).

Isolation of β -sitosterol and isofucosterol: Successive elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (95:5) yielded a mixture of sterols (sterol-1) (300 mg). The separation was carried out on plc (preparative layer-chromatography) of their acetates on 5% AgNO₃-impregnated silica gel G plates to yield β -sitosterol acetate (1; 80.0 mg), m.p. 127° (ir, nmr, ms), and isofucosterol acetate (2; 210 mg), m.p. 130° (lit.⁶ 132°, ir, nmr, ms).

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